
ASSESSMENT OF PESTICIDE RESIDUES IN LIVESTOCK PRODUCTS AND THEIR PUBLIC HEALTH NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

**Haruna E.A.^{1,2,*}, Alhaji N.B.^{1,2}, Adama Y.J.¹, Onakpa M.M.^{1,3},
Hadiza L.M.¹, Hussaini A.M.¹**

¹*Africa Center of Excellence for Mycotoxins and Food Safety Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria*

²*Livestock Productivity and Resilience support (LPRES) Project Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries Minna, Niger State, Nigeria*

³*Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria.*

**Corresponding Author: Email- aliyuevuti1@gmail.com; contact: +2348039709760*

ABSTRACT

Pesticide residues in milk, meat, and the environment pose significant food safety concerns, particularly for vulnerable populations like children and pregnant women, due to risks such as congenital defects. This study assessed pesticide levels in cattle blood, milk, and edible tissues (muscle, liver, kidney, and tongue) from abattoirs in Niger State using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry. Total pesticide residue levels were 1.331 µg/kg in muscle, 2.124 µg/kg in liver, 1.908 µg/kg in kidney, 2.017 µg/kg in tongue, 3.22 µg/kg in milk, and 1.845 µg/kg in blood, with the residue order being Muscle > Blood > Kidney > Tongue > Milk. Detected pesticides included Methomyl (0.068 µg/kg), Carbofuran (0.037 µg/kg), Acetamiprid (0.021 µg/kg), Parathion (0.039 µg/kg), and Aldrin (0.322 µg/kg), among others. The presence of obsolete and highly toxic pesticides like Carbofuran, Parathion, and α -Lindane raises significant public health alarms due to their bioaccumulation and persistence, underscoring the lack of regulatory monitoring in developing countries like Nigeria, where food safety standards are often inadequate. This highlights the urgent need for continuous monitoring, stringent regulations, and mitigation strategies to reduce health risks and enhance food safety. The absence of effective pesticide monitoring, especially for locally consumed and export-bound products, undermines public health and economic prospects. By providing essential baseline data, this study aims to promote compliance with international standards and safeguard consumers from pesticide-related risks.

Keywords: Cattle meat; Food Safety; Health Risk; Public Health, Pesticide

INTRODUCTION

The increasing reliance on pesticides in Nigeria to enhance food security and manage agricultural pests raises significant concerns regarding environmental contamination and human health risks. While pesticides are essential for controlling agricultural threats, their widespread use has led to bioaccumulation of toxic residues in the environment, posing risks to non-target organisms and ecosystems (Angaye *et al.*, 2022; Anjaria *et al.*, 2024). These residues accumulate in livestock products, leading to health hazards for consumers, particularly through dietary intake (Mdeni *et al.*, 2022). Livestock exposure occurs through direct application, inhalation of contaminated air, and ingestion of contaminated feed and soil (Anjaria *et al.*, 2024), resulting in the transfer of toxic substances up the food chain. Pesticides disrupt essential biological processes, causing ecological damage, biodiversity loss, and toxicity in aquatic and terrestrial organisms (*Tudi *et al.*, 2021; *Naharki *et al.*, 2020; Sean *et al.*, 2022).

The persistence of these chemicals in the environment leads to long-term ecological imbalances, with effects such as teratogenicity, genotoxicity, and a decline in beneficial organisms like pollinators (Arora *et al.*, 2022; Hashimi *et al.*, 2020). The accumulation of fat-soluble pesticides in tissues such as milk, blood, and fat magnifies their impact throughout the food chain, posing serious health risks including neurotoxicity, chronic poisoning, and cancer (Mehta *et al.*, 2020; Victoria *et al.*, 2022; Adedokun *et al.*, 2023). Residues in livestock products, especially milk and meat, highlight the urgent need for effective monitoring and regulation to safeguard human and animal health

(Archibong *et al.*, 2023; Ujuamala *et al.*, 2022).

In Nigeria, significant pesticide residue levels in food underscore the urgent need for regulatory measures and public awareness campaigns to mitigate risks (Li *et al.*, 2022; Lopes *et al.*, 2021; Gurbuz *et al.*, 2024). Studies reveal that residues in livestock tissues enter the food chain, exacerbating chronic health effects and promoting pest resistance due to indiscriminate pesticide use (Oliveira *et al.*, 2022). Strengthening regulatory frameworks, promoting sustainable agricultural practices, and conducting informed research are vital to ensuring food safety and addressing pesticide-related challenges in Nigeria (Morowati *et al.*, 2022; Nag *et al.*, 2005). Ensuring the safety of the livestock subsector, which contributes significantly to Nigeria's GDP and protein intake, is imperative through surveillance and compliance with international standards (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2015; Tongo *et al.*, 2015).

The aim of the Study is therefore to determine residue levels of pesticides in animal products (Milk, Muscle, Kidney, Liver, Tongue). and evaluate public health impact on the consumption of milk contaminated with pesticide residues

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Niger State, Nigeria, located in the North-central geopolitical zone within the Southern Guinea Savannah ecological area. Covering approximately 76,363 square kilometers, it is the largest state in Nigeria by land mass. The state comprises three agro-ecological zones: Zone A (Southern)

with eight local government areas (LGAs), Zone B (Eastern) with nine LGAs, and Zone C (Northern) with eight LGAs. Niger State has an estimated cattle population of 2.4 million.(Fig.1)

This cross-sectional survey involved collecting samples of blood, meat, tongue, liver, milk and kidney.

Figure 1. Map of Niger State showing the three Agro-zones in the state

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size was determined using the formula by Thrusfield (2009) at 95 % confidence interval.

$$N = Z^2 \times pq / d^2$$

Where, N = number of the required sample size, Z = standard deviation at 95 % confidence interval or 1.96, P = the power or prevalence (50%), q = 1 – p; d = the degree of confidence (0.05)

N = required sample size is Z = Z-score corresponding to desired confidence level 1.96 p = estimated proportion of the population that has a particular characteristic is 0.906 d = desired margin of error is 0.05.

$$N = (1.96)^2 \times 0.906 \times 0.094 = 3.8416 \times 0.08516 = 130$$

Additional contingency of 20 making total sample = 150

Sampling Tools and Sample Collection

Muscle, Kidney, Blood, Tongue and liver samples were collected from cattle slaughtered at major abattoirs in the state. Blood, milk and urine samples were collected at the pastoral herd sites.

Sampling

Sample stations

The sample stations were Minna abattoir (9°46'83" N and 6°54'33" E), Bida abattoir (9°08'53" N and 6°02'03" E), and Suleja abattoir (9°13'75" N and 7°20'14" E) located in Niger State, Northern Nigeria. These abattoirs were chosen because they serve most markets in Niger State. Samples were collected from January–March, 2024.

A total of 150 samples of blood, milk, and four edible cattle parts: muscle, liver, kidney, and tongue tissues were collected from the three abattoirs. Samples were wrapped in polythene bags, labelled, placed on ice and sent to the laboratory. Samples were then stored at -20 °C until analysis. A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted.

Sample Preparation and Analysis

Sample Preparation

The article outlines a detailed methodology for the collection, storage, and analysis of samples for pesticide residue detection using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The research was carryout at the Chemical laboratory of Afe Babalola University Edo-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Samples were collected and stored in sterile polythene bags, then transported to the laboratory where they were homogenized. Fifty grams of the homogenized sample were extracted with a solvent mixture (hexane) and processed to remove water using sodium sulfate. The extract was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and prepared for cleanup through Florisil column chromatography. The cleaned-up samples were then analyzed using GC-MS.

Chemicals used included analytical grade

acetone, n-hexane, dichloromethane, and HPLC grade acetonitrile, with standards for various pesticides sourced from Ehrenstorfer GmbH. The GC-MS analysis employed a DB-5 fused silica capillary column with nitrogen as the carrier gas. The oven temperature followed a specific program, and the mass spectrometer operated in electron impact ionization mode. Selected ion monitoring (SIM) was used for higher specificity and sensitivity.

Quality controls (QCs) were regularly injected to assess repeatability. Standard curves were plotted for quantification, and the samples were injected as one batch to minimize variations. The glassware used was meticulously cleaned to prevent contamination. Reagents for residue analysis were sourced from various suppliers, including Agilent and Sigma Aldrich.

The determination of pesticide residue followed the QuEChERS method (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe) with slight modifications to accommodate the number of analytes. This method, based on AOAC Method 2007.01, was used to ensure accurate and efficient analysis of pesticide residues in the samples.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

Sample Analysis and Human Health Risk Assessment

Sample Analysis

Following sample cleanup, aliquots of the final volume were quantified using a GC-MS (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) LC-10 ADvp, equipped with an SPD-M 10 Avp attached to a PDA (Shimadzu SPD-M 10

Avp, 200–800 nm). The analytical column was a C18 Reverse Phase Alltech (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm), maintained at 30°C in a column oven. The mobile phase consisted of 70% acetonitrile (ACN) and 30% water, filtered using a 0.45 µm cellulose filter before each use. The flow rate was set at 1.0 mL/min, with all solvents used being of HPLC grade. Prior to HPLC analysis, samples were passed through 0.45 µm nylon syringe filters (Alltech Associates, IL, USA). Twenty microliters of each sample were manually injected. The identification of suspected pesticides was performed relative to the retention time of the pure analytical standard, and quantification was based on methods described by Chowdhury et al. (2012a, 2012b).

Human Health Risk Assessment

Health risk estimates for pesticide residues in cattle tissues were computed using three standard indices: the Estimated Average Daily Intake (EADI),

The EADI was calculated by multiplying

the residual pesticide concentration in the cattle tissue (mg/kg) by the meat consumption rate (8.6 g/day in Nigeria, FAO, 2004) and dividing the result by the body weight (Fianko, 2011). Two hypothetical age/weight categories were used: 1–11 years/30 kg for children and 70 kg for adults. The EADI was expressed as mg/kg/day. The EADIs were compared with established acceptable daily intakes (ADI) by USEPA (1996) to assess long-term risk from exposure to pesticide residues through meat consumption (Pardio, 2012; FAO/WHO, 2009; Tchounwou, 2002).

Data Management and Statistical Analyses

The data collected from the study were collated, tabulated, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0 (Standard Version SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution tables and percentages, were used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Table 1. Detected pesticides from the gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of meat muscle tissue sample

Peak	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp µg/kg	M/z
1	6.00	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	4.35	0.068	45, 88, 162
2	8.00	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	8.26	0.037	64, 149, 221
3	10.21	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	10.87	0.021	42, 58, 222
4	13.00	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	18.48	0.076	43, 208, 373
5	13.75	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	1.09	0.039	41, 97, 291
6	14.73	a-Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	2.61	0.093	51, 183, 290
7	16.00	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	0.65	0.036	77, 252, 281
8	17.23	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	20.65	0.105	57, 161, 218
9	19.00	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	1.74	BDL	97, 197, 350
10	20.40	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	1.21	0.027	57, 176, 311
11	24.87	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	9.13	0.063	65, 100, 373
12	26.82	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	2.61	0.235	69, 195, 406
13	27.41	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	13.91	0.322	66, 263, 364
14	32.18	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ PS	416	1.09	ND	91, 163, 416
15	36.50	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	1.52	0.213	79, 180, 380
16	37.28	?-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	2.17	BDL	51, 181, 449

MW= molecular Weight, M/z = mass-to-charge ratio

A total of 16 pesticides were identified by the gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of muscle (meat) with most of the compound showing high activity as represented by their peaks and extensive percentage area in the chromatogram. The identified reactive pesticides are Methomyl (4.35%), Carbofuran (8.26 %), Acetamiprid (10.87%), Profenofos (18.48%), Parathion (1.09 %), α -Lindane (2.61 %), Pendimethalin (0.65%), Propanil (20.65

%), Chlorpyrifos (1.74 %), Butachlor (0.87 %), Heptachlor (9.13 %), Endosulfan (2.61%), Aldrin (13.91%), Cypermethrin (1.09%), Dieldrin (1.52%), λ -Cyhalothrin (2.17 %). Of the pesticides detected by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis, Propanil was the highest with percentage area of 20.65 % while Pendimethalin has the least percentage area of 0.65 %. (Table 1).

Table 2. Detected pesticides from the gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of liver tissue sample

Peak #	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp μ g/kg	M/z
1	6.00	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	4.55	0.036	45, 88, 162
2	8.00	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	8.79	0.215	64, 149, 221
3	10.21	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	10.90	0.100	42, 58, 222
4	13.00	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	18.78	1.075	43, 208, 373
5	13.75	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	0.91	BDL	41, 97, 291
6	14.73	α -Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	2.73	0.024	51, 183, 290
7	16.00	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	0.61	ND	77, 252, 281
8	17.23	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	21.82	0.114	57, 161, 218
9	19.00	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	2.42	0.013	97, 197, 350
10	20.40	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	1.21	0.037	57, 176, 311
11	24.87	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	9.09	0.283	65, 100, 373
12	26.82	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	1.82	0.162	69, 195, 406
13	27.41	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	9.70	0.037	66, 263, 364
14	32.18	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ PS	416	1.52	BDL	91, 163, 416
15	36.50	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	2.12	0.015	79, 180, 380
16	37.28	?-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	3.03	0.013	51, 181, 449

MW= molecular Weight, M/z = mass-to-charge ratio

A total of 16 pesticides were identified by the gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of muscle (meat) with most of the compound showing high activity as represented by their peaks and extensive percentage area in the chromatogram. The identified reactive pesticides are Methomyl (4.55%), Carbofuran (8.79 %), Acetamiprid (10.87%), Profenofos (18.78%), Parathion (0.91 %), α -Lindane (2.73 %), Pendimethalin (0.61%), Propanil (21.82

%), Chlorpyrifos (2.42 %), Butachlor (1.21 %), Heptachlor (9.09 %), Endosulfan (1.82 %), Aldrin (9.70 %), Cypermethrin (1.52%), Dieldrin (2.12%), λ -Cyhalothrin (3.03 %). Of the pesticides detected by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis, Profenofos was the highest with percentage area of 20.65 % while Pendimethalin has the least percentage area of 0.61 %. (Table 2).

Table 3. Gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of pesticides residues detected in kidney tissue sample

Peak #	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp µg/kg	M/z
1	6.98	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	3.90	0.026	45, 88, 162
2	11.50	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	7.15	0.200	64, 149, 221
3	12.00	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	9.43	0.090	42, 58, 222
4	13.50	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	10.78	0.643	43, 208, 373
5	16.21	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	6.50	0.021	41, 97, 291
6	16.32	α-Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	10.41	0.028	51, 183, 290
7	19.75	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	10.08	0.014	77, 252, 281
8	20.40	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	14.96	0.214	57, 161, 218
9	24.87	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	7.48	0.019	97, 197, 350
10	24.92	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	4.55	0.021	57, 176, 311
11	29.98	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	6.50	0.297	65, 100, 373
12	31.27	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	4.23	0.185	69, 195, 406
13	31.60	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	1.46	0.140	66, 263, 364
14	37.00	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ PS	416	2.28	BDL	91, 163, 416
15	37.25	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	1.95	0.015	79, 180, 380
16	38.04	λ-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	2.93	BDL	51, 181, 449

MW= molecular Weight, M/z = mass-to-charge ratio

A total of 16 pesticides were identified by the gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of muscle (meat) with most of the compound showing high activity as represented by their peaks and extensive percentage area in the chromatogram. The identified reactive pesticides are Methomyl (3.90%), Carbofuran (7.15%), Acetamiprid (9.43%), Profenofos (10.78%), Parathion (6.50%), α-Lindane (10.41%), Pendimethalin (10.08%), Propanil (14.96

%), Chlorpyrifos (7.48%), Butachlor (4.55%), Heptachlor (6.50%), Endosulfan (4.23%), Aldrin (1.46%), Cypermethrin (2.28%), Dieldrin (1.95%), λ-Cyhalothrin (2.93%). Of the pesticides detected by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis, Propanil was the highest with percentage area of 14.96% while Aldrin has the least percentage area of 1.46%. (Table 3).

Table 4. Detected pesticides from the gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of tongue tissue sample

Peak #	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	M/z
1	6.98	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	3.85	0.023	45, 88, 162
2	11.50	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	7.05	0.208	64, 149, 221
3	12.00	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	6.62	0.087	42, 58, 222
4	13.50	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	10.90	1.000	43, 208, 373
5	16.21	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	6.41	0.018	41, 97, 291
6	16.31	α -Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	8.01	0.031	51, 183, 290
7	19.75	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	10.88	0.024	77, 252, 281
8	20.40	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	9.93	0.106	57, 161, 218
9	24.87	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	5.93	0.011	97, 197, 350
10	24.92	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	7.69	0.026	57, 176, 311
11	29.98	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	6.73	0.293	65, 100, 373
12	31.27	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	4.49	0.137	69, 195, 406
13	31.60	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	1.44	0.037	66, 263, 364
14	37.00	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ PS	416	2.24	BDL	91, 163, 416
15	37.25	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	1.92	0.017	79, 180, 380
16	38.04	?-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	2.88	BDL	51, 181, 449

MW= molecular Weight, M/z = mass-to-charge ratio

A total of 16 pesticides were identified by the gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of muscle (meat) with most of the compound showing high activity as represented by their peaks and extensive percentage area in the chromatogram. The identified reactive pesticides are Methomyl (3.33%), Carbofuran (6.10%), Acetamiprid (9.15%), Profenofos (9.43%), Parathion (11.10%), α -Lindane (8.32%), Pendimethalin (8.88%), Propanil (12.48

%), Chlorpyrifos (5.55%), Butachlor (6.38%), Heptachlor (6.66%), Endosulfan (4.02%), Aldrin (2.22%), Cypermethrin (1.94%), Dieldrin (2.08%), λ -Cyhalothrin (3.36%). Of the pesticides detected by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis, Pendimethalin was the highest with percentage area of 10.88% while Aldrin has the least percentage area of 1.44%. (Table 4).

Table 5. Detected pesticides from the gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of blood sample

Peak #	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$	M/z
1	6.98	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	3.33	0.020	45, 88, 162
2	11.50	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	6.10	0.20	64, 149, 221
3	12.00	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	9.15	0.071	42, 58, 222
4	13.50	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	9.43	1.872	43, 208, 373
5	16.21	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	11.10	0.016	41, 97, 291
6	16.32	α -Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	8.32	0.028	51, 183, 290
7	19.75	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	8.88	0.020	77, 252, 281
8	20.40	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	12.48	0.113	57, 161, 218
9	24.87	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	5.55	0.014	97, 197, 350
10	24.92	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	6.38	0.021	57, 176, 311
11	29.98	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	6.66	0.298	65, 100, 373
12	31.27	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	4.02	0.128	69, 195, 406
13	31.60	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	2.22	0.030	66, 263, 364
14	37.00	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ PS	416	1.94	BDL	91, 163, 416
15	37.25	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	2.08	0.014	79, 180, 380
16	38.04	?-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	3.36	BDL	51, 181, 449

MW= molecular Weight, M/z = mass-to-charge ratio

The GC-MS analysis of blood samples revealed exposure to various pesticides, highlighting potential health and environmental risks. Profenofos showed the highest concentration (1.872 µg/kg) and a peak area of 9.43%, indicating significant exposure to this organophosphate with neurotoxic properties. Parathion, with a lower concentration of 0.016 µg/kg but a peak area of 11.10%, also highlights potential acute toxicity. Carbofuran (0.20 µg/kg, 6.10% peak area) and Methomyl (0.020 µg/kg, 3.33% peak area) pose severe risks due to their high toxicity. Persistent organic pollutants such as α -Lindane (0.028 µg/kg, 8.32% peak area), Heptachlor (0.298 µg/kg, 6.66% peak area), Aldrin (0.030 µg/kg, 2.22% peak area), and Dieldrin (0.014 µg/kg, 2.08% peak area) raise concerns about bioaccumulation and carcinogenic potential. Endosulfan (0.128 µg/kg, 4.02% peak area) and Pendimethalin (0.020

µg/kg, 8.88% peak area) highlight environmental contamination risks, with Endosulfan being particularly hazardous as an endocrine disruptor. Acetamiprid (0.071 µg/kg, 9.15% peak area) could impact human health and pollinators, while Chlorpyrifos (0.014 µg/kg, 5.55% peak area) and Butachlor (0.021 µg/kg, 6.38% peak area) are associated with neurodevelopmental and hormonal disruptions. Propanil (0.113 µg/kg, 12.48% peak area) raises concerns for oxidative stress, while Cypermethrin (below detectable limit, 1.94% peak area) and λ -Cyhalothrin (below detectable limit, 3.36% peak area) emphasize risks from chronic exposure. This analysis underscores the need for stringent pesticide regulation, public health education, and comprehensive environmental risk assessments to mitigate exposure and safeguard ecosystems. (Table 5)

Table 6. Detected pesticide residues from the gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of milk sample

Peak #	Retention Time	Compound Detected	Mol. Formula	MW	Peak Area %	Comp µg/kg	M/z
1	2.48	Methomyl	C ₂ H ₈ NOPS ₂	162	3.35	0.032	45, 88, 162
2	4.00	Carbofuran	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221	7.53	0.030	64, 149, 221
3	4.25	Acetamiprid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	222	5.32	BDL	42, 58, 222
4	5.78	Profenofos	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₃ PS	373	6.21	BDL	43, 208, 373
5	8.50	Parathion	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ NO ₅ PS	291	13.30	1.112	41, 97, 291
6	13.24	α -Lindane	C ₆ H ₆ Cl ₆	290	17.29	0.025	51, 183, 290
7	13.50	Pendimethalin	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	281	2.22	0.027	77, 252, 281
8	14.50	Propanil	C ₉ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	218	9.76	0.114	57, 161, 218
9	16.62	Chlorpyrifos	C ₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ NO ₃ PS	350	4.43	BDL	97, 197, 350
10	17.28	Butachlor	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ ClNO ₂	311	0.22	0.019	57, 176, 311
11	25.50	Heptachlor	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	373	8.68	0.013	65, 100, 373
12	25.27	Endosulfan	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₆ O ₃ S	406	9.31	0.846	69, 195, 406
13	25.60	Aldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆	364	5.76	0.039	66, 263, 364
14	27.00	Cypermethrin	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ PS	416	2.66	0.014	91, 163, 416
15	27.65	Dieldrin	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₆ O	380	1.77	0.032	79, 180, 380
16	33.08	?-Cyhalothrin	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	449	2.00	ND	51, 181, 449

A total of 16 pesticides were identified by the gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis of muscle (meat) with most of the compound showing high activity as represented by their peaks and extensive percentage area in the chromatogram. The identified reactive pesticides are Methomyl (3.33%), Carbofuran (7.53%), Acetamiprid (5.32%), Profenofos (6.21%), Parathion (13.30%), α -Lindane (17.29%), Pendimethalin (2.22%), Propanil (9.76%), Chlorpyrifos (4.43%), Butachlor (0.22%), Heptachlor (8.68%), Endosulfan (9.31%), Aldrin (5.76%), Cypermethrin (0.914%), Dieldrin (2.08%), λ -Cyhalothrin (2.00%). Of the pesticides detected by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) analysis, α -Lindane was the highest with percentage area of 17.29% while Cypermethrin has the least percentage area of 0.014%. (Table 6).

Different pesticide classes found in the livestock product across the state

The assessment of pesticide residues in livestock products in Niger State, Nigeria, revealed contamination across multiple pesticide classes, including organophosphates (methomyl, profenofos, parathion, chlorpyrifos), organochlorines (α -lindane, heptachlor, endosulfan, aldrin, dieldrin), carbamates (carbofuran), neonicotinoids (acetamiprid), herbicides (pendimethalin, propanil, butachlor), and pyrethroids (cypermethrin, λ -cyhalothrin) (FAO, 2023; WHO, 2021). These residues were found in milk, muscle, kidney, liver, and tongue samples, raising significant public health concerns due to their association with neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, liver damage, and potential carcinogenicity (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022; Ekanem *et al.*, 2024). The presence of

organochlorines, despite their ban or restriction, suggests environmental contamination or illegal usage (Okoli *et al.*, 2020), while other pesticides reflect improper application and bioaccumulation in livestock (Adegoke *et al.*, 2022). The chronic exposure risks, particularly to vulnerable groups like children, underscore the need for stringent regulatory enforcement, public awareness campaigns, and promotion of safer pest management practices (Usman *et al.*, 2023; EFSA, 2023). These findings highlight the urgency of addressing pesticide contamination to safeguard public health and ensure food safety in the region.

To calculate the human health risk of consuming the indicated food items from the cattle, we need to consider the following factors:

To predict the health risk of Dichlorvos exposure for children and adults consuming milk contaminated with Dichlorvos, we can use the Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) and compare it with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI).

Given Data

Concentration of Dichlorvos in milk

©: 1,097 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (which is 1.097 mg/kg since 1 μg = 0.001 mg)

Body Weight (BW): 15 kg for children, 50 kg for adults

Intake Rate (IR) of milk: 0.6 kg/day for children, 0.75 kg/day for adults

Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI): 0.0001 mg/kg body weight

Step 1: To calculate the Estimated Daily Intake (EDI)

The Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) is calculated using the formula:

$$EDI = \frac{C_x IR}{B_w}$$

where:

C_x = Concentration of Dichlorvos in milk (mg/kg)

IR = Intake rate of milk (kg/day)

B_w = Body weight (kg)

For Children (15 kg body weight):

$$EDI_{\text{children}} = \frac{1.097 \times 0.6}{15} = \frac{0.6582}{15} = 0.04388 \text{ mg/kg body weight/day}$$

For Adults (50 kg body weight):

$$EDI_{\text{Adult}} = \frac{1.097 \times 0.75}{50} = \frac{0.82275}{50} = 0.016455 \text{ mg/kg body weight/day}$$

Step 2: Compare EDI with ADI to Assess Risk

Now, to compare the EDI to the ADI of 0.0001 mg/kg body weight/day:

For Children:

$$\text{Risk}_{\text{Children}} = \frac{EDI_{\text{Children}}}{ADI} = \frac{0.04388}{0.0001} = 438.8$$

Haruna et al., 2025 76

For Adult:

$$\text{Risk}_{\text{Adult}} = \frac{EDI_{\text{Adult}}}{ADI} = \frac{0.016455}{0.0001} = 164.55$$

Step 3: Interpretation

The calculated risk ratios indicate that both children and adults are exposed to levels of Dichlorvos that significantly exceed the acceptable daily intake. Specifically, children are exposed to approximately 438.8 times the ADI, while adults are exposed to about 164.55 times the ADI. This suggests a substantial health risk associated with the consumption of milk contaminated with Dichlorvos at the specified concentration.

Given these findings, it is crucial to implement measures to reduce pesticide residues in food products, particularly in milk, to safeguard public health, especially for vulnerable populations such as children

Sarojmoni et al. (2022), Damalas & Eleftherohorinos, 2011).

DISCUSSION

The presence of pesticide residues in milk, such as aldrin and carbofuran, represents a significant public health concern, especially considering the widespread consumption of milk and dairy products. Aldrin (C₁₂H₈Cl₆), an organochlorine pesticide, was extensively used in mid-20th-century agriculture. Although its use has been banned in many countries due to its persistence and associated health risks, aldrin residues continue to be detected in animal tissues, raising concerns about the

long-term implications of environmental contamination (Morais, 2011).

Aldrin is rapidly metabolized into dieldrin in the body, a process that influences its distribution within animal tissues. Studies have shown that although lower concentrations of aldrin residues are found in the liver (0.0458 µg/kg) and muscle, higher levels in the kidney and tongue suggest ongoing environmental exposure (Fianko, 2011). This pattern indicates that the animals might be exposed to aldrin-contaminated feed or water sources, which is concerning given aldrin's toxic nature. Even at concentrations within regulatory limits, aldrin poses significant health risks due to its potential for biomagnification, where it accumulates in fatty tissues over time. This accumulation leads to chronic exposure in humans, especially in those who consume large quantities of dairy products, which can result in severe health issues such as carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity, and disruption of the endocrine system (USEPA, 2005; ATSDR, 2002). The persistence of aldrin in the environment, coupled with its ability to enter and magnify within the food chain, underscores the need for stringent monitoring and control measures to minimize exposure and protect public health.

Similarly, carbofuran (C₁₂H₁₅NO₃), a carbamate insecticide, is associated with significant environmental and food safety concerns. Carbofuran has been widely used in agriculture due to its effectiveness in controlling pests, but its toxicity to non-target organisms, including humans, is well-documented (Morais, 2011). The residue distribution of carbofuran in animal tissues typically shows higher levels in the tongue compared to other

organs such as the muscle, liver, and kidney. This distribution pattern is likely due to the tongue's direct exposure to xenobiotics, making it a primary site for residue accumulation (Shahzadi, 2013).

Long-term exposure to carbofuran, even at low levels, has been linked to a range of adverse health effects, including neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and immunotoxicity. These effects highlight the critical need for rigorous monitoring and regulation of carbofuran residues in food products. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) has identified carbofuran as highly toxic, particularly to children and fetuses, necessitating its inclusion in strict regulatory frameworks to ensure that food products, especially those consumed by vulnerable populations, are safe (USEPA, 1996; USEPA, 2008).

The detection of aldrin and carbofuran residues in livestock products like milk is a clear indication of the ongoing risks posed by pesticide contamination in the food chain. The potential for bioaccumulation and the associated health risks necessitate robust surveillance systems to monitor pesticide levels in food products, enforce compliance with regulatory standards, and protect public health (Adeyemi et al., 2015; de Albuquerque et al., 2020). Moreover, there is a need for public awareness campaigns to educate consumers on the risks associated with pesticide residues and to promote safer agricultural practices that minimize the use of harmful pesticides.

In conclusion, the presence of aldrin and carbofuran residues in milk highlights the critical importance of continuous monitoring and stringent regulation of pesticide use in agriculture. As the

evidence shows, even low levels of these chemicals can have profound health implications, reinforcing the need for a comprehensive approach to food safety that includes regular residue testing, stricter enforcement of pesticide regulations, and the promotion of sustainable farming practices that reduce reliance on harmful chemicals. Such measures are essential to safeguard public health and ensure the safety of the food supply (de Albuquerque et al., 2020; Fianko, 2011).

Table(1) reveals a concerning level of contamination, with several pesticides exceeding acceptable limits and potentially posing significant risks to public health and food safety. The detection of pesticide residues in meat, such as Aldrin (0.322 µg/kg), Endosulfan (0.235 µg/kg), Dieldrin (0.213 µg/kg), Profenofos (0.076 µg/kg), and Parathion (0.039 µg/kg), poses significant health risks. Aldrin, a persistent organochlorine pesticide, is classified by the WHO as "probably carcinogenic to humans" (Group 2A) and bioaccumulates in the food chain, posing severe health threats. Endosulfan, with known neurotoxic and endocrine-disrupting effects, has been linked to developmental problems in children and reproductive issues in adults. The EPA has banned Endosulfan due to its health risks. Dieldrin, another organochlorine pesticide, is a probable human carcinogen (Group B2) and is highly toxic, linked to cancer, neurological disorders, and reproductive problems. Profenofos, an organophosphate insecticide, can inhibit the enzyme cholinesterase, leading to neurological issues and is classified by the EPA as "likely to be carcinogenic to humans" (Group B2). Parathion, a highly toxic organophosphate, is banned in many

countries due to its acute toxicity and potential long-term health effects and is classified by the WHO as "extremely hazardous." Although pesticides like Chlorpyrifos, λ-Cyhalothrin, Methomyl, Carbofuran, Acetamiprid, Pendimethalin, Propanil, Butachlor, Heptachlor, and Cypermethrin were below detection limits or not detected, they remain concerning due to their known toxicities. The presence of these residues indicates a potential breakdown in food safety protocols, eroding consumer trust and posing risks, especially to vulnerable populations. This necessitates stricter regulatory enforcement, sustainable agricultural practices, and consumer education to ensure a safer food system. For further reading, refer to the WHO's International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS) on Aldrin, and the EPA's information on Endosulfan, Dieldrin, Profenofos, and Parathion.

CONCLUSION

Total pesticide residues level of 1.331 µg/kg (muscle), 2.124 µg/kg (liver), 1.9078 µg/kg (kidney), 2.017 µg/kg (tongue), 3.22 mg/ml (milk) and 1.845 mg/ml (blood) was found to be above Acceptable Daily Intake and MRL (96.91%). Respondent agreed that Long-term, high-intensity use of pesticides can bring about an imbalance in ecosystems disruption of ecological balance and collapse of biodiversity, pesticide resistance, and economic issues.

Herbicide is the commonest pesticide in used in the study area and there is poor knowledge and awareness of public health implications of pesticides. Most respondents (95.88%) were ignorant of various health effects of pesticide bio-magnification in humans which include carcinogenicity, teratogenicity,

immunosuppression, embryotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, and hepatotoxicity the survey data underscores the consistent recognition of pesticide-related challenges. The alignment with established literature emphasizes the urgency of informed policies, integrated pest management, and public awareness campaigns to ensure sustainable and responsible pesticide usage.

Recommendations

- * **Policy and Regulation:** Stricter enforcement of pesticide application standards and residue monitoring in animal-derived food products is essential.
- * **Public Awareness:** Education campaigns should be launched to

inform producers and consumers about the risks associated with pesticide contamination.

- * **Further Research:** Longitudinal studies should evaluate the long-term health effects of low-dose pesticide exposure from animal products.
- * **Mitigation Strategies:** Adoption of safer pesticide alternatives and integrated pest management practices can reduce environmental contamination.

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